

A DETERMINISTIC APPROACH OF THE RUPTURE, APPLICATION
TO THE CASES OF HIGH-MODULUS CARBON FIBERS AND OTHER
CERAMIC FIBERS.

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ABSTRACT

Most statistical strength analyses are carried out using a Weibull distribution function. Apart from some very specific and generally unrealistic cases of defect population in the material, there is however no reason that this approach ever leads to a better prediction of size effect than it does, for instance, in the studied cases of HM carbon or alumina-zirconia fibers. A new deterministic approach is proposed. This method gives directly from experimental strength measurements a quantitative representation of the critical defect distribution in the material as a function of their failure propensity. Consequently, it permits e.g. precise predictions of the experimental strength distributions at other gauge lengths or after annealing treatment or damaging, as well as a very significant optimization of the testing procedure in determining the only necessary gauge lengths at which strength measurements have to be performed to allow a complete description of the defect population and consequently a confident strength prediction at any gauge length. Various and new applications of strength analyses for understanding fracture mechanisms are proposed in cases of HM carbon, mullite and alumina-zirconia fibers.

KEYWORDS: Strength Distribution; Failure Probability; Defect Population; Size Effect; Reinforcing Fibers.

1. INTRODUCTION

To characterize the strength of composite reinforcing fibers, strength measurement series are performed on single fibers in various conditions as, different sizes or different states of damage. A large scatter of the measured data at fixed conditions is generally observed. Moreover, the average strength generally decreases when the size of the tested samples - for instance, the gauge length - increases, as a result of a higher probability to find a critical defect leading to early rupture. For the prevision of the strength distribution in other conditions, a - if possible - "phenomenological" model has to be used.

The strength values obtained at fixed conditions (e.g. fixed gauge length or precise annealing treatment) are arranged in ascending order. At the stress σ_i corresponding to the i^{th} strength measurement among n performed, the cumulative failure probability is assumed to be equal to $F(\sigma_i) = \frac{i-0.5}{N}$ [1]. At the gauge length L_0 , n points $(\sigma_i, F(\sigma_i))$ are determined. The fitting of this experimental strength distribution with a Weibull distribution function (see equation (1) (cf fig. 1) should theoretically allow the prediction of strength distribution in other conditions as, e.g., other gauge lengths, since it is the hypothesis of the Weibull model that the material is well described [2]. However, this last assumption is sometimes totally unrealistic, and applied to the case of Al-coated HM carbon or alumina-zirconia fibers, the Weibull statistics does not lead to any convenient prediction of the size effect, as shown on table 1. The Weibull cumulative failure probability $F(\sigma)$ at stress σ is given by:

$$F(\sigma) = 1 - \exp\left[-\left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0(L)}\right)^m\right] \quad (1)$$

TABLE 1. Determination of the Weibull fitting parameters where the scale parameter $\sigma_0(L)$ must verify:

$$\ln \sigma_0(L) = K - \frac{1}{m} \cdot \ln L \quad (2)$$

(L = fibre length, m = shape parameter, K = material's intrinsic value)

2. A NEW DETERMINISTIC APPROACH OF THE RUPTURE

Since the Weibull statistics appears to be unable to represent the material and its fracture mechanisms, a deterministic method of describing rupture probability has been developed [3] and applied to the characterization of different reinforcing fibers. It is based on a precise description of the real population of defects, deduced from the analysis of the measured strength distribution, and no longer on an idealized and a priori simplified distribution as proposed by the Weibull model. It assumes that what is observed is what is to be observed and does not only result from experimental errors. For instance, a jump in the strength distribution at the stress level σ_c , which must be considered in the Weibull approach like a statistical deviation from the defined relation $F(\sigma)$ (see equation (1)), must in fact reveal a high concentration of specific defects in the material which break at their critical stress σ_c (called σ_c -defects) (fig. 2). Consequently, the analysed material may be characterized, in terms of strength, by its population of σ_c -defects. Since the rupture at the stress level σ can only be observed when there is at least one σ -defect and no more critical defect than this one in the tested fiber, the deduced probability density to find a σ -defect in a L_0 -fiber (fiber of gauge length L_0) is:

$$f(\sigma) = \left[1 - \exp\left(-\frac{dP_r^\sigma(\sigma)}{1 - P_r^\sigma}\right) \right] / \left[\int_{\sigma_1}^{\sigma_n} \left\{ 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{dP_r^\sigma(\sigma)}{1 - P_r^\sigma}\right) \right\} d\sigma \right] \quad (3)$$

Experimentally, through tensile tests of L_0 -fibers, only a part of this defect population can then be observed. The prediction of a strength distribution at the gauge length L from the

experimental distribution Pr^0 can thus be made in the strength dispersion band observed at the length L_0 according to (4):

$$P_r(L, \sigma) = 1 - \exp\left[\int_0^\sigma \ln\left(1 - g\left(\frac{L}{L_0} \left(1 - \exp - \frac{dP_r^0(\sigma_c)}{d\sigma}(\sigma_c)\right)\right)\right) d\sigma_c\right] \quad (4)$$

$$\text{where } g(x) = \begin{cases} x & \text{if } x \leq 1 \\ 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

3. APPLICATION TO THE CASE OF Al-COATED HM-CARBON FIBER

As presented on fig. 3, two experimental distributions can already give a wide description of the defect population of the material: 2.5 mm, the smallest tested gauge length and 20 mm which allows an optimal scanning of the critical defect dispersion. The σ_c -defect ($\sigma_c \approx 3.0$ GPa) corresponding to the failure probability of 20% for the gauge length 2.5 mm, are corresponding to a failure probability of 75% for the gauge length 20 mm. The more critical defects ($\sigma_c < 3.0$ GPa) are observed through the strength measurements at 20 mm, the less critical ones ($\sigma_c > 3.0$ GPa) at 2.5 mm. To describe a new complementary part of the critical defect distribution, if it exists, it would be optimal to test an additional series of 30 single fibers at the new gauge length of 150 mm. This is at present experimentally unrealizable.

The observed defect population is concentrated around some critical stress levels (1.8 - 2.4 - 2.7 - 3 - 3.2 - 4 GPa). The strength distribution at a new length predicted from the experimental distributions, according to (4), must consequently present jumps too at these values. For example, the distribution at 2.5 mm has been calculated from the experimental one at 20 mm. The perfect fitting with the experimental curve at 2.5 mm is noteworthy (fig. 4).

Since a defect can be distinguished from the others by its critical stress value σ_c (σ_c -defect) or, what is equivalent, its order of appearance (failure probability P) and its probability of presence in the tested fiber (height of jump ΔP) ($P_{\Delta P}$ -defect), it is possible to determine the influence of damaging on each

defect and then, possibly to extrapolate this influence on other potential, but not observed more critical, defects which would determine the strength of a bundle or a composite material.

At temperature above 500°C in vacuum, HM carbon fibers react with aluminium to form aluminium carbide Al_4C_3 [4]. The mechanism is diffusion controlled and therefore dependent on time and temperature [5]. Thus, when the same batch of fibers (with the same gauge length in order to observe the same defects) undergoes a stronger annealing treatment, the carbide crystal roots grow within the fiber, preferentially on active sites like surface defects, causing a variation of the defect critical stresses. This results in horizontal translations of the distribution curves as observed on fig. 5, for failure probabilities between 0.25 and 0.75. The influence of annealing treatment is similar for both populations of defects defined in fig. 5. The relative critical stress has a local maximum at (600°C for 30 min) (fig. 6).

4. CONCLUSION AND OTHER APPLICATIONS

It has been demonstrated that the new deterministic method offers a significantly more precise description of the actual fracture strength distribution and it offers better predictive capability than does the standard Weibull statistics. Applied very successfully in the case of Al-coated HM-carbon fibers, this approach has allowed an explanation of the apparent absence of size-effect on the strength distribution of studied alumina-zirconia fibers: they contain only two populations of defects close to the critical stress of 1.7 GPa (fig. 7). This case is fully incompatible with the classical statistical model of rupture. Conversely, in the case of the analysed mullite fibers, the Weibull approach is sufficient in terms of size-effect prediction. The peaks in the determined defect distribution curves are not well reproduced from one gauge length to the other. According to this new approach, it must however be concluded that there is no very characteristic (or precise) defect population in those fibers: that has clearly been observed on scanning electron micrographs which show a lot of differently

shaped and sized volume defects from one fracture surface to another (fig. 8).

Nevertheless, it remains more interesting to analyse rupture in terms of critical defect population rather than in determining statistical fitting parameters considering the material as a black-box.

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⁽¹⁾ mean value. ⁽²⁾ calculated from equation (2)

L(mm)		2.5	5.5	10	20	40	80	m ⁽¹⁾	m ⁽²⁾
carbon (HM35)	σ_0	3796	3029	2826	2760	2795	2643	6.0	11.5
	m	7.5	4.4	4.8	6.3	6.9	6.2		
L(mm)			6	9		30	45	m ⁽¹⁾	m ⁽²⁾
mullite (Nextel480)	σ_0		2033			1548		4.8	5.9
	m		5.4			4.3			
alumina zirconia (PRD166)	σ_0			1684			1658	5.8	103
	m			5.2			6.5		

FIGURE 1. Weibull Correlation curves of Al-coated HM-carbon fibers experimental strength distributions at the two extreme gauge lengths

FIGURE 2. Observation of a critical defect in a HM-carbon fiber (SEM)

FIGURE 3. Strength and observed defects distributions at different gauge lengths (HM-carbon fibers)

FIGURE 4. Application of the approach to the prediction of strength distributions at other gauge lengths

FIGURE 5. Al-coated HM-carbon fiber after annealing treatment at 600°C

population 1

population 2

FIGURE 6. Iso-temperature critical stress of $P_{\Delta P}$ -defects

FIGURE 7. Strength and observed defects distributions at different gauge lengths (alumina zirconia fibers)

FIGURE 8. Fracture surfaces of the mullite fiber (STEM images of various kinds of defects)